

DATA COLLECTION OVERVIEW

This phase is divided into three sub-phases:

1. Supply data collection tools

The first important step revolves around all those activities to procure, deploy, and install the Telraam technology. Ideally, this should be conducted as part of a physical workshop with participants (including hands-on activities as explained above) where, at the end of the event, people can take their sensors and will have experienced a demonstration of the registration and installation process, as well as a detailed technical explanation of how the sensor works and what its limitations are.

Tool, the WeCount Toolbox: to support home delivery of the sensors (but also suitable for physical handover), a WeCount Toolbox has been designed and developed. It consists of a cardboard box to be sent to participants (or handed over if done face to face) including: the sensor, the step-by-step installation guide; the Sensing Diary (see section 3.3.2); the charger and the additional equipment and manuals. The cardboard box is 22x15x9 cm and includes a paper wrap with WeCount logo and the following text: *Citizen Toolkit to Count Traffic and Mobility*.

2. Complement data collected from sensors with qualitative data from participants

The Telraam sensing technology and platform provide and visualise data about traffic in a given location. This includes how many cars, pedestrians, bicycles, and heavy vehicles pass in front of a given window and at what speed. However, some specific contingency factors (e.g. road closure for temporary works, events such as protests, marathons, among many others) may affect the analysis, interpretation, and ultimately the findings from the data collected. Thus, the main goal of this sub-phase is to propose an approach to enable effective interpretation of the data provided by the sensors, by including qualitative data from participants. The tool proposed to do this is named the WeCount Sensing Diary.

3. Provide continuous support (technical and non-technical) to participants

An aspect of paramount importance during the months of data collection is to provide the right amount of technical and non-technical support to participants. While establishing communication channels (e.g. e-mails, WhatsApp groups with community champions etc.) is an important, and quite obvious, aspect of this sub-phase, a more structured, scalable, and embedded online resource has been developed. The system is called Zendesk. In WeCount, the Zendesk platform was available for all partners and complemented the very much needed one-to-one conversations with participants experiencing doubts and issues.

Tool, Zendesk: in terms of providing continuous support to participants, an embedded set of resources has been developed within Zendesk and is now integrated in the Telraam website. The system includes several different elements

to facilitate interactions and tracking of activities. Also, it provides organised and structured Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) comprehensively covering technical, procedural, maintenance-related, and privacy and security elements